

**CHARACTERISTIC VIBRATIONS OF A CYLINDRICAL SHELL
LOCATED IN A DEFORMABLE MEDIUM**

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Abstract: In this work, the characteristic oscillations of a cylindrical shell in an infinitely elastic medium are investigated by solving the problem of plane deformation of the theory of elasticity. The paper presents the formulation, methodology and algorithm for solving the problem. With the help of special functions, the transcendental equation of the characteristic frequency is obtained in analytical form. Numerical results were obtained and analyzed using the Muller method.

Аннотация: В данной работе исследованы характеристические колебания цилиндрической оболочки в бесконечно упругой среде путем решения задачи плоской деформации теории упругости. В работе представлены постановка, методология и алгоритм решения задачи. С помощью специальных функций получено трансцендентное уравнение характеристической частоты в аналитическом виде. Численные результаты были получены и проанализированы с использованием метода Мюллера.

Annotatsiya: Bu ishda cheksiz elastik muhitda joylashgan silindrik qobiqning xos tebranishlari elastiklik nazaryasining tekis deformatsiya masalasiga olib kelinib yechilgan. Ishda masalaning qo'yilishi, yechish metodikasi va algoritimi keltirilgan. Analitik formada xos chastotaning transendent tenglamasi, maxsus funktsiyalar orqali olingan. Sonli natijalar Myuller usuli yordamida olingan va tahlil qilingan.

Key words: medium, shell, frequency, absorption condition, wave potentials.

Ключевые слова: среда, оболочка, частота, условие поглощения, волновые потенциалы.

Kalit so'zlar: muhit, qobiq, chastota, yutilish sharti, to'lqin potensialari.

INTRODUCTION

Typical vibrations of rods and shells located in an elastic medium are considered and solved in [1,2,3]. In these works, the medium surrounding the rod and shells is replaced by an elastic spring. Similarly, in [4], the characteristic oscillation of a spherical body located in an elastic medium is studied.

The oscillation of the points of the medium satisfies the Lamé equation of the theory of elasticity. Numerical results were obtained and analyzed in the work. In this paper, instead of the Sommerfeld absorption condition at infinity, it is recommended to use its abbreviated condition.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

The equation of motion of a cylindrical shell satisfies the Kirchhoff-Lava hypothesis for the plane question of elasticity theory and takes the following form:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial \theta^2} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial \theta} &= -\frac{R^2}{B} x_1 \\ \frac{\partial u}{\partial \theta} + b^2 \left(\frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial \theta^4} + 2 \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial \theta^2} + w \right) + w &= \frac{R^2}{B} x_2 \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Here $x_1 = -\sigma_{r\theta} \Big|_{r=R} - \rho_o h_o \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2}$; $x_2 = -\sigma_{rr} \Big|_{r=R} - \rho_o h_o \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial t^2}$;

$$b^2 = \frac{h_o^2}{12R^2}; \quad B = \frac{E_o h_o}{1 - \nu_o^2};$$

$$\sigma_{r\theta}|_{r=R} = \mu_c \left\{ 2 \left[\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial^2 \varphi}{\partial \theta \partial r} - \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial \theta} \right] + \left[\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \theta^2} - r \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial r} \right) \right] \right\} \Big|_{r=R}$$

$$\sigma_{rr}|_{r=R} = \left\{ \lambda_c \nabla^2 \varphi + 2\mu_c \left[\frac{\partial^2 \varphi}{\partial r^2} - \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \theta} \right) \right] \right\} \Big|_{r=R}$$

$$\nabla^2 \varphi = \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 \varphi}{\partial \theta^2}$$

In this R - average radius of the shell surface, ρ_o - shell density, ν_o - the Poisson's ratio of the shell, E_o - modulus of elasticity of the shell, σ_{rr} and $\sigma_{r\theta}$ - components of the normal and tangential stress of the medium, indicating the shell. The φ_c , ψ_c longitudinal and transverse potentials of the medium surrounding the shell satisfy the wave equation

$$\nabla^2 \varphi_c = \frac{1}{c_{c1}^2} \frac{\partial^2 \varphi_c}{\partial t^2}, \quad (2)$$

$$\nabla^2 \psi_c = \frac{1}{c_{c2}^2} \frac{\partial^2 \psi_c}{\partial t^2}.$$

in this $c_{c1}^2 = (\lambda_c + 2\mu_c) / \rho_c, c_{c2}^2 = \mu_c / \rho_c$.

The condition of contact between the medium and the shell is the condition of equality of displacements and stresses:

$$u \Big|_{r=R} = u_\theta \Big|_{r=R}, \quad w \Big|_{r=R} = u_r \Big|_{r=R}. \quad (3)$$

For sliding contact conditions

$$w \Big|_{r=R} = u_r \Big|_{r=R}, \quad \sigma_{r\theta} \Big|_{r=R} = 0. \quad (4)$$

The system of differential equations (2) and its solution r for $r \rightarrow \infty$ satisfy the following condition:

$$\lim_{r \rightarrow \infty} (\sqrt{r}) \left(\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial r} + i\alpha \phi \right) = 0 \quad \lim_{r \rightarrow \infty} (\sqrt{r}) \left(\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial r} + i\beta \psi \right) = 0 \quad (5)$$

where α and β – wave numbers, $\alpha^2 = \frac{\omega^2}{c_1^2}$, $\beta^2 = \frac{\omega^2}{c_2^2}$.

SOLUTION METHOD AND NUMERICAL RESULTS

We are looking for a solution to the wave equations (2) in the following form

$$\begin{pmatrix} u \\ w \\ \varphi \\ \psi \end{pmatrix} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \begin{pmatrix} V_n(R) \\ W_n(R) \\ \phi_n(r) \\ \psi_n(r) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \sin n\theta \\ \cos n\theta \\ \cos n\theta \\ \sin n\theta \end{pmatrix} \cdot e^{-i\omega t}, \quad (6)$$

in this $\omega = \omega_R + i\omega_I$ – complex characteristic frequency; $V_n(R), W_n(R)$ – amplitude displacement function; $\phi_n(r), \psi_n(r)$ – the amplitude function of migration potentials satisfies the Helmholtz equations.

$$\nabla^2 \phi_n + \alpha^2 \phi_n = 0, \nabla^2 \psi_n + \beta^2 \psi_n = 0$$

The solutions of the Helmholtz equations are expressed in terms of the 1 and 2 native Hankel function:

$$\phi_n = A_{n1} H_n^{(1)}(\alpha r) + B_{n1} H_n^{(2)}(\alpha r), \quad \psi_n = A_{n2} H_n^{(1)}(\beta r) + B_{n2} H_n^{(2)}(\beta r), \quad (7)$$

here A_{ni} ($j=1, 2$) and B_{ni} – are arbitrary constants and are found from (5) and (6) boundary conditions; $H_n^{(1)}(K_i r)$, $H_n^{(2)}(K_i r)$ – 1 and 2 native n-th ordinal Hancel function. We will analyze the solution presented above (6). Let's look at the following private solution

$$\phi_n = \text{Re} \left[e^{-i\omega t} H_0^{(1)}(\alpha r) \right] \quad (8)$$

The argument of this function for large values of r for $H_0^{(1)}(\alpha r)$ the function has the following asymptotic formula

$$H_0^{(1)}(\alpha r) \approx \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi \alpha r}} \left[1 + O(r^{-1}) \right].$$

Here $O(r^\alpha)$ such a ratio of magnitude is defined that, when $r \rightarrow \infty$ striving, the $\frac{y}{r^{\alpha k}}$ ratio retains its limitations, taking into account these relations; the following expression can be obtained:

$$\phi_1 = \text{Re} \left[\sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi \alpha r}} e^{i(\alpha r - \frac{\pi}{4} - \alpha t)} \cdot [1 + O(r^{-1})] \right] = \left[\sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi \alpha r}} \cos \omega \left(t - \frac{r}{c} + \frac{\pi}{4} \right) \right] \cdot [1 + O(r^{-1})].$$

This function expresses a wave moving away from the body at a speed of c at $r \rightarrow \infty$ [5]. Similarly, it can be shown that the second term in solution (6) also has a physical meaning $\phi_2 = \text{Re} [e^{-i\omega t} H_0^{(2)}(\alpha r)]$. This term represents a wave approaching a body from infinity. If the $r \rightarrow \infty$ Sommerfeld absorption condition is used, then $B_{n1} = B_{n2} = 0$. As an example, let's look at the vibrations of an unconsolidated space located in an infinitely elastic medium. Then the condition for $r = R$ voltage relief is established, i.e.

$$\sigma_{rr} \Big|_{r=R} = \sigma_{r\theta} \Big|_{r=R} = 0. \tag{9}$$

If (6) and (7) are taken into account and inserted into the boundary condition (8), we obtain a system of homogeneous algebraic equations with complex coefficients. In order for this homogeneous system of equations to have a solution, its main determinant, composed of coefficients before unknowns, must be zero, the elements of the main determinant are a function of a complex parameter ω . From this relation we obtain the same frequency equation as for determining the complex parameter ω .

$$D_n = x H_{n-1} \left[(n^2 - 1) y H_{n-1}(y) - (n^3 - n + y^2 / 2) H_n(y) \right] - H_n(x) \left[(n^3 - n + y^2 / 2) y H_{n-1}(y) - (n^2 + n - y^2 / 4) y^2 H_n(y) \right] = 0, \tag{10}$$

here $x = \omega R(\rho / (\lambda + 2\mu))^{1/2}$; $y = \omega R(\rho / \mu)^{1/2}$, λ and μ - Lamé coefficients; ρ - material density. After simple substitutions, we bring the above (9) equation to the transcendental equation

$$(n^2 - 1)F(x)F(y) - (y^2 / 2)F(x) + F(y) + n^2 - (n^2 - y^2 / 2)^2 = 0, \tag{11}$$

here $F(x) = x H'_n(x) / H_n(x)$, $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$

Table 1: Change in the complex frequency with respect to n

	n = 0	n = 1	n = 2	n = 3
	0,4529D + 00	0,10927D + 01	0,19075D + 01 -i0,89782D + 00	0,27565D + 01

	-i0,47651D + 00	-i0,76538D + 00		-i0,99155D + 00
			0,28621D + 00 -i0,17852D + 00	0,72325D + 01 -i0,32283D + 01
			0,404607D + 00 -i0,178552D + 00	0,12307D + 00 -i0,22283D + 00

The complex parametric frequency equation (10) is solved using the Muller method. This is a transcendental equation (10), the roots of which consist of two parts: real ($\text{Re } \Omega$) and imaginary ($\text{Im } \Omega$).

The real part of the complex frequency represents the oscillation frequency of the mechanical system, and the abstract part expresses the damping coefficient. The calculation results $n \geq 0$ ($\nu_1 = 0,25$) are shown in Table 1.

CONCLUSION

Since the results are analyzed in the table, it can be noted that with an increase in n , the real and abstract parts of the complex frequency also increase. (10) the frequency equation will depend only on the Poisson's ratio (ν). It was found that when changing the value of the Poisson's ratio in the range from $0 \leq \nu \leq 0.4$, up to 27% of the actual and minimum parts of the frequency change.

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